

Early Prediction of Liver Diseases using Machine Learning models and Ensemble techniques

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Abstract.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has changed something so that it is much better in various aspects of our lives, offering solutions to numerous problems and bridging gaps between reality and business. Liver disease encompasses a wide range of conditions that impair the liver's ability to function properly, leading to serious health issues. In the early stages, liver disease is often without symptoms, making early detection and intervention crucial. Advanced liver disease can result in liver failure, and in some cases, a liver transplant may be necessary. If the liver disease can be detected in early life, certain preventive measures can be taken so that the patient can recover from liver disease and can enjoy a real and happy life. This paper intends to create a liver disease predictive model utilizing medical data and investigating the impact of various factors on the condition using machine learning techniques. Accurate prediction models for liver disease risk assessment have been created using a variety of machine learning methods, such as Decision Trees, Random Forests, and Support Vector Machines. The main causes of the development of liver diseases have been determined by looking into disease influence measures. Here machine learning models and ensemble methods of machine learning models have been applied for selecting a proper model for prediction of liver disease of the person. Under machine learning models Random forest, decision tree, gradient boosting, KNN(K nearest neighbour), logistic regression have been used. Under ensemble methods, voting classifier using maximum voting, average voting, Blending, Bagging and boosting, stacking of models have been used.

Keywords.

machine learning models, Random forest, decision tree, gradient boosting, KNN(K nearest neighbor), Ensemble techniques, voting classifier using maximum voting, average voting, Blending, Bagging and boosting.

1.Introduction.

Early detection of liver disease is essential for effective treatment. Advanced imaging methods, such as elastography (including FibroScan), aid in assessing liver stiffness, which may indicate fibrosis or cirrhosis. Blood biomarkers like ALT, AST, and specialized liver function tests are commonly used to evaluate liver health. Recently, researchers have explored non invasive biomarkers and genetic markers for their potential in predicting disease progression, especially in conditions like NAFLD and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH).

2. Literature Review.

Ruhul Amin [1] employed projection-based feature extraction techniques to reduce data redundancy. The Indian Liver Patient Dataset (ILPD) from the University of California, Irvine (UCI) repository was used to classify chronic liver disease. Peter Ifeoluwa Adegbola [2] utilized data collected from rats exposed to environmentally concerning chemicals. Linear regression techniques were applied to extract significant features for predicting the probability of disease occurrence, followed by the use of random forest (RF) classification to determine disease likelihood. Similarly, Osama Mohareb Khaled [3] implemented three machine learning models—K-nearest neighbors (KNN), Gaussian Naïve Bayes, and random forest—on a dataset comprising 32,000 records. Their findings indicated that the random forest model outperformed

the other algorithms.

Trupti M. Kodinariya [4] analyzed ultrasonic images, computerized tomography (CT) scans, and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data, applying both machine learning and deep learning techniques for liver disease detection. Likewise, Srilatha Tokala [5] employed logistic regression, support vector machines, K-nearest neighbors, and random forest algorithms, with random forest demonstrating superior performance compared to the others.

Engy A. El-Shafeiy [6] used KNN, Gaussian Naïve Bayes (Gaussian NB), and random forest (RF) classifiers, reporting that the random forest model yielded the best performance. Similarly, Barinderjit Kaur [7] worked with a dataset of 416 patients from an Indian hospital and developed a hybrid model combining KNN and random forest for liver disease prediction. Additionally, Neha Tanwar [8] utilized a liver patient dataset to predict liver disorders using machine learning models such as support vector machines, logistic regression, K-nearest neighbors, and random forest. Among these, random forest exhibited the highest accuracy. Shahid Mohammad Ganie [9] analyzed a dataset containing 23 attributes and 7,000 patient records collected from the Egyptian Liver Research Institute and Mansoura Central Hospital in Egypt. He employed support vector machines (SVM), Boosted C5.0, and Naïve Bayes (NB) data mining techniques for liver disease prediction.

Finally, R. Kalaiselvi [10] conducted a comprehensive survey on the application of various machine learning algorithms for liver disease prediction. The study explored both supervised and unsupervised learning techniques for improving disease diagnosis.

The proposed approach by the authors integrates Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) for sequence learning and Convolution Neural Networks (CNNs) for extracting non-linear features [12]. This methodology enhances the analysis of the Mammographic Image Analysis Society (MIAS) dataset, achieving improvements of 5% in accuracy, 6% in precision, and 4.6% in recall.

Mammography has demonstrated promising outcomes with the application of deep learning technologies in the quantitative evaluation of parenchymal density, categorization, detection, diagnosis, and breast cancer risk prognosis, enabling more precise patient management [13]. Additionally, deep learning has streamlined the interpretation process, reducing both interpretation time and workload.

This paper presents a comparative analysis of segmentation and feature extraction methods for detecting lung cancer [14]. Various segmentation techniques, such as Thresholding, global Thresholding, and watershed segmentation, are implemented and assessed. Additionally, feature extraction is applied to improve the performance of these segmentation techniques. Segmentation, detection, and classification are essential stages in digital imaging pathology labs for analyzing MRI brain tumour regions. This study focuses on medical image analysis and classification using a convolution+ReLU algorithm, which integrates convolutional techniques with ReLU optimization [15]. The research employs a robust and efficient convolution+ReLU approach on the BraTS 2020 dataset, significantly reducing segmentation time compared to other optimization methods. Researchers process extensive and complex healthcare data using various deep learning techniques, enabling medical professionals to predict diseases effectively [16]. This study introduces a model designed to identify cardiac disorders, aiming to benefit numerous individuals globally. The proposed model enhances the Convolution Neural Network (CNN), referred to as Custom CNN (C-CNN), and demonstrates superior performance compared to previously published methods.

The authors have concentrated on machine learning (ML) algorithms for cancer prediction, which is impacted by various performance metrics [17]. By utilizing widely used ML techniques such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Linear Regression, Decision Tree, and Naive Bayes, the study evaluates the accuracy of cancer prediction.

In this study, the authors propose enhancing a MobileNet base model by fine-tuning it with additional features to improve brain tumour detection [18].

Since insulin plays a crucial role in regulating various properties of plasma, including water, enzymes, proteins, vitamins, and minerals, its imbalance can lead to diabetes [19]. Diabetes is one of the most prevalent chronic diseases worldwide. This research considers both clinical and non-clinical factors, such as insulin levels, glucose, BMI, smoking, stress, blood pressure, and dietary habits like junk food consumption. Existing methods [20] for medical image feature extraction have proven insufficient in effectively addressing the challenges of early brain tumour detection. To overcome this limitation, a novel model leveraging the Inception-v3 convolution neural network has been proposed. The authors introduce an automated identification method that leverages deep learning and visual analysis technology [21]. Their approach classifies fundus images using a convolution neural network (CNN) based on the severity of diabetic retinopathy (DR). The article presents a fuzzy distance-based ensemble approach integrating deep learning models for cervical cancer detection in Pap smear images [22]. The methodology employs three transfer learning models—Inception V3, MobileNet V2, and Inception ResNet V2—enhanced with additional layers to capture data-specific features. This paper presents a systematic literature review of pneumonia detection techniques that incorporate transfer learning alongside other methodologies [23]. The review protocol is meticulously designed to identify recent research on pneumonia detection from the past five years. Following an extensive search process, 35 studies were selected for analysis. This study introduces a novel approach utilizing Deep Separable Convolution Neural Networks (DS-CNNs) to enhance Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) prediction [24]. Using the Chronic Kidney Disease Dataset from Kaggle, the proposed model integrates DS-CNNs with advanced optimization techniques to improve predictive accuracy. DS-CNNs employ depth wise and pointwise convolutions to enable efficient feature extraction and classification while maintaining computational efficiency. The authors introduce and evaluate an innovative method for heart disease prediction by integrating deep learning models with bioinspired algorithms [25]. Deep learning techniques facilitate automatic feature extraction and the recognition of complex patterns from raw data, while bioinspired algorithms enhance optimization, improving model accuracy and generalization. This study by the authors introduces an IoMT-enabled approach for lung disease detection and classification, leveraging deep learning techniques to analyze lung sounds [26]. The proposed method utilizes three datasets: the Respiratory Sound, the Corona hack Respiratory Sound, and the Coswara Sound. To benchmark performance, traditional machine learning models such as the Extra Tree Classifier and AdaBoost Classifier are employed. Imbalanced classification presents a significant challenge in early disease detection and diagnosis using machine learning, often leading to reduced accuracy due to the disproportionate distribution of positive cases compared to healthy individuals [27]. To enhance classification accuracy, this study proposes an architectural model that incorporates a modified Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) with Minkowski distance and entropy-based weighting to determine the number of synthetic samples to generate.

This study explores the use of a hybrid Autoencoder-LSTM (AE-LSTM) model to enhance the detection of Diabetic Nephropathy (DN) [28]. The Autoencoder (AE) component compresses clinical data while preserving essential features and reducing dimensionality, whereas the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network captures temporal dependencies and sequential patterns, improving feature learning for early diagnosis.

This study presents an innovative approach to colon cancer diagnosis by integrating autoencoder-based feature selection, Capsule Networks (CapsNets), and histopathology images to address existing challenges [29]. CapsNets effectively capture spatial hierarchies in visual data, enhancing pattern recognition and classification accuracy. This study introduces a

versatile framework that utilizes a lightweight Convolution Neural Network (CNN) architecture to automate lung and colon cancer diagnosis in histopathological images across various diagnostic scenarios [30]. The commonly used LC25000 dataset, comprising 25,000 histopathological images classified into five categories—lung adenocarcinoma, lung squamous cell carcinoma, benign lung tissue, colon adenocarcinoma, and benign colonic tissue—serves as the foundation for this research.

This research presents an innovative chest X-ray classification framework that utilizes a fine-tuned VGG19 model (16 layers) enhanced with Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) for improved contrast, binary mask attention to emphasize abnormalities, and advanced data augmentation techniques for enhanced generalization [31]. A key feature of this approach is the implementation of a Probabilistic U-Net for lung segmentation, which isolates critical features while employing weighted masks to focus on pathological regions. This study introduces the Hierarchical Reinforcement Learning with Multi-Expert Feedback (ME-RL) framework aimed at enhancing automated disease diagnosis within dialogue systems [32]. The framework employs a hierarchical structure with lower-level networks incorporating a reward model. In this setup, a discriminator, inspired by adversarial networks, evaluates the authenticity of symptom query sequences generated by the agent, providing rewards accordingly. This study [33] utilizes the Mask R-CNN semantic segmentation technique, incorporating a ResNet-50 backbone, to analyze CT scans of COVID-19 patients. The model is trained on an annotated dataset, improving its capability to accurately segment and delineate the lung parenchyma in CT images. The study investigates the efficacy of combining various resampling techniques with machine learning algorithms to improve prediction accuracy in imbalanced heart and lung disease datasets [34]. The authors integrate under sampling methods, such as Edited Nearest Neighbours (ENN) and Instance Hardness Threshold (IHT), with oversampling techniques like Random Oversampling (RO), Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE), and Adaptive Synthetic Sampling (ADASYN). Glaucoma, a primary cause of irreversible blindness, is marked by characteristic changes in the optic disk. While manual assessments remain valuable, they are hindered by subjectivity, inconsistencies, and the significant time required for evaluation [35]. With the advent of artificial intelligence, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) models have emerged as powerful tools for automated and improved optic disk analysis. A neural network, a fundamental component of artificial intelligence, is designed to emulate the structure and function of the human brain [36]. It consists of interconnected nodes, or artificial neurons, organized into layers that process information sequentially. This research contributes to ongoing efforts in cardiovascular disease (CVD) detection by utilizing two powerful machine learning techniques: Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) and K-Nearest Neighbours (K-NN) [37]. The shift from traditional in-person classrooms to online learning environments has introduced challenges for both educators and students [38]. In virtual settings, instructors often concentrate on delivering content without real-time awareness of students' emotional states, potentially leading to decreased engagement and increased feelings of fatigue and disinterest among learners.

The authors [39] introduce a novel diagnostic framework that integrates a one-dimensional convolution neural network (CONV1D) with an enhanced long short-term memory (LSTM) model. Machine learning (ML) technology [40] identifies patterns linked to specific diseases by analyzing extensive datasets containing patient records, including diabetes, blood pressure, cholesterol levels, X-rays, MRIs, CT scans, imaging data, and genomic information. ML algorithms assess key symptoms to determine disease presence.

Predicting heart disease accurately is crucial for timely medical intervention. Machine learning (ML) techniques, particularly those involving feature selection and dimensionality reduction, have shown promise in enhancing diagnostic precision [41].

This research explores the use of machine learning models to anticipate heart disease by analyzing key health indicators collected from patients [42]. It employs Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for dimensionality reduction and SVM for classification. The objective is to enable early identification of cardiac issues to help prevent fatalities. PCA simplifies complex datasets, while SVM enhances the accuracy of predictions. In a recent study, researchers applied Principal Component Analysis (PCA) in conjunction with four wrapper-based feature selection methods—Forward Feature Selection (FFS), Backward Feature Selection (BFS), Exhaustive Feature Selection (EFS), and Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE)—to two versions of the Cleveland heart disease dataset, referred to as D1 and D2[43]. They evaluated the performance of four classifiers: K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Random Forest (RF), Decision Trees (DT), and XGBoost. Cardiovascular disease ranks among the leading causes of death worldwide, making early detection critically important. This study proposed a supervised learning approach to predict heart disease at an early stage using patients' medical records [44]. A classification model has been developed by combining Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with the Decision Tree algorithm to analyze and categorize medical data.

The study focuses on enhancing heart disease diagnosis by extracting significant information from the UCI Machine Learning Repository's heart disease dataset [45]. The approach integrates Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and regression techniques to identify key features influencing heart disease.

3. Motivation.

A lot of research work ([1] - [9], [12] - [45]) have been done in the area of healthcare prediction with an objective to detect sickness of various organs. Machine learning algorithms have also been proposed ([1], [2], [4] - [6], [12], [17], [19], [37]). Deep Learning models have been proposed in {[9], [16], [22], ([24]-[26])}, Segmentation has been done in ([9], [14], [33]). Dimension Reduction Analysis has been done in ([41]- [45]). However, no author has worked on the same data set and not evaluated several evaluation measures. That is the reason for this proposed work which has been written in this paper. Here an effort is being made to work using dimension reduction analysis method along with machine learning techniques on lever disease data set with an objective to select a particular model suitable for the data set. After selecting suitable model, it is necessary to find out the disease affected persons so that in course of time, the concerned person may be recovered with application of proper medicine and food and other items as the case may be.

4. Data set.

The lever data set has been collected from UCI Machine Repository ([11]). The data set comprises of 7 attributes. These are furnished below :-

Table 1
Lever Data Set

No	Attribute Code	Attribute Information
1	mcv	mean corpuscular volume
2	alkphos	alkaline phosphotase
3	sgpt	alamine aminotransferase
4	sgot	aspartate aminotransferase
5	gammagt	gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase
6	drinks	number of half-pint equivalents of alcoholic beverages drunk per day

7	selector	field used to split data into two sets viz. healthy or diseased.
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5. Methodology.

5.1. Random Forest.

Random Forest is a classifier that contains a number of decision trees on various subsets of the given dataset and takes the average to improve the predictive accuracy of that dataset. Instead of relying on one decision tree, the random forest takes the prediction from each tree and based on the majority votes of predictions, and it predicts the final output.

5.2. Decision tree

Decision Trees are flowchart-like tree structures of all the possible solutions to a decision, based on certain conditions. It is called a decision tree as it starts from a root and then branches off to a number of decisions just like a tree. The tree starts from the root node where the most important attribute is placed. The branches represent a part of entire decision and each leaf node holds the outcome of the decision.

5.3. KNN(K Nearest Neighbours) algorithm: It is one of the simplest and widely used classification algorithms in which a new data point is classified based on similarity in the specific group of neighbouring data points.

5.4. Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machine(SVM) is a supervised machine learning algorithm. It can be used in both classification and regression problems. Inherently, it is a discriminative classifier. Given a set of labelled data points, an SVM tries to separate the data points into different output classes. It does so by finding an optimal hyper plane that distinctly classifies the data points into an N-dimensional space (N - the number of features).

5.5. Linear Regression.

Linear regression tries to model the relationship between two variables by fitting a linear equation to the available data. One variable is taken as an explanatory variable, and the other is called as dependent variable. The form of the regression equation with one dependent and one independent variable is defined as $y = c + b*x$, where y is considered as dependent variable score, c = constant, b = regression coefficient, and x = an independent variable Which takes a number of values.

5.6 Ensemble Methods.

Ensemble learning is a machine learning technique that enhances accuracy and resilience in predicting by merging predictions from multiple models. It aims to minimize errors or biases that may exist in individual models by combining the collective intelligence of the ensemble models. Under ensemble techniques, max voting, average voting and weighted averaging have been used. The hierarchy of the ensemble techniques has been found in figure 2.

5.6.1. Max Voting.

In this technique, multiple models make predictions for each data point. Each model's predictions count as a 'vote.' The majority of the models' predictions determine the final prediction.

5.6.2. Average Voting.

Multiple predictions are made for each data point in averaging. An average of predictions from all the models are taken to make the final prediction.

5.6.3. Weighted Average.

Different weights assign to all models, defining the importance of each model for prediction.

5.6.4. Stacking.

Stacking is an ensemble learning technique that uses predictions from multiple models to build a new model. This model makes predictions on the test set. Build the decision tree and KNN models at level zero, while construct a logistic regression model at level one.

5.6.5. Blending.

Blending follows the same approach as stacking but uses a holdout (validation) set from the train set to make predictions. In other words, unlike stacking, predictions can be made only on the holdout set. Use the holdout set and the predictions to build a model that runs on the test set.

5.6.6. Bagging.

Blending follows the same approach as stacking but uses only a holdout (validation) set from the train set to make predictions. In other words, unlike stacking, you make predictions only on the holdout set. Use the holdout set and the predictions to build a model that runs on the test set.

Bootstrapping is a sampling technique in which we create subsets of observations are created from the original dataset, with replacement. The size of the subsets is the same as the size of the original set.

The Bagging (or Bootstrap Aggregating) technique uses these subsets (bags) to provide a fair idea of the distribution (complete set). The size of subsets created for bagging may be less than the original set.

Initially multiple subsets of data are created from the original dataset by selecting observations with replacement. A base model (weak model) is created on each of these subsets. The models run in parallel and are independent of each other.

5.6.7. Boosting.

Boosting is a sequential process, where each subsequent model attempts to correct the errors of the previous model. The succeeding models are dependent on the previous model.

A subset is created from the original dataset. Initially, all data points are given equal weights. A base model is created on this subset. This model is used to make predictions on the whole dataset.

Under Boosting algorithms AdaBoost, GBM, XGBM, Light GBM, CatBoost algorithms have been used.

5.6.7.1. Bagging meta-estimator.

The bagging meta-estimator serves as an ensembling algorithm that you can use for both classification (Bagging Classifier) and regression (Bagging Regressor) problems. It follows the typical bagging technique to make predictions. Under bagging meta-estimator, random subsets are created from the original dataset (Bootstrapping). The subset of the dataset includes all features. A user-specified base estimator is fitted on each of these smaller sets.

Predictions from each model are combined to get the final result.

5.6.7.2. Adaboost.

Adaptive boosting or AdaBoost is one of the simplest boosting algorithms. Usually, models use decision trees for modeling. The process creates multiple sequential models, with each model correcting errors from the previous one. AdaBoost assigns weights to incorrectly predicted observations, and the subsequent model aims to predict these values accurately.

5.6.7.3. Gradient Boosting

Gradient Boosting or GBM is another ensemble machine learning algorithm that works for both regression and classification problems. GBM uses the boosting technique, combining a number of weak learners to form a strong learner. Regression trees used as a

base learner, each subsequent tree in series is built on the errors calculated by the previous tree.

5.6.7.4. XGBoost

XGBoost (extreme Gradient Boosting) is an advanced implementation of the gradient boosting algorithm. It is a highly effective ML algorithm, extensively used in machine learning competitions. XGBoost has high predictive power and is almost 10 times faster than the other gradient boosting techniques. It also includes a variety of regularization which reduces overfitting and improves overall performance. Hence it is also known as “regularized boosting” technique.

5.6.7.5. Light GBM

Light GBM is a gradient boosting framework that uses tree-based algorithms and follows leaf-wise approach while other algorithms work in a level-wise approach pattern. Compared to the other algorithms, Light GBM takes lesser time to run on a huge dataset.

Simple Ensemble Techniques and Advanced Ensemble Techniques
Figure 1

6. Contribution.

Proposed Flow of Work

Step 1. Data Collection. Lever data set Data have been collected from [11]

Step 2. The dataset containing relevant information for the prediction of disease of lever have been taken.

Step 3. The data have been entered accurately and completely.

Step 4. Data Pre-processing: Cleaning of data and Removal of Outlier have been done.

Step 5. Taking care of missing data by input certain concerned data or removal of that data based on the nature and quantity of missing values.

Step 6. Cleaning the data by tackling inconsistencies, errors, and anomalies.

Step 7. Detection and removal of outliers that may affect the analysis.

Step 8. Implementation of Machine Learning models and Performance Evaluation:

Step 9. Under machine learning classifier models, Random forest classifier, Decision Tree classifier, Support Vector Machine (Linear), Logistic Regression, Gaussian Naïve Bayes, K Nearest Neighbours have been used.

Step 10. Train the classifiers using the pre-processed data.

Step 11. Evaluate the performance of each classifier using evaluation metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

Step 12. Application of Ensemble Methods and Performance Evaluation:

Step 13. Ensemble methods include Simple Ensemble Methods and advanced Ensemble Techniques.

Step 14. Under Simple Ensemble Methods Max Voting, Averaging and Weighted Average techniques have been used.

Step 15. Evaluate each simple ensemble model based on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score to assess the effectiveness of each approach.

Step 16. Under Advanced technique Stacking, Blending, Bagging, Boosting have to be used.

Step 16. Bagging includes Meta Estimator and Random Forest.

Step 17. Boosting includes Adaboost classifier, Adaboost Regressor, GBM Classifier, GBM Regressor, XGBoost Classifier, XG Boost Regressor, Light GBM.

Step 18. Evaluate each advanced ensemble model based on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score to assess the effectiveness of each approach.

Step 19. Train each ensemble models using the pre-processed data.

Step 20. Evaluate the performance of each ensemble method and compare the results.

Step 21. Compare and analyse the performance of all the different techniques employed in previous steps (Machine Learning models and Ensemble Techniques).

Step 22. Evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score to assess the effectiveness of each approach

Step 23. Identify the most accurate and reliable method for predicting the lever disease based on the results as obtained.

6.1. Classification.

6.2. Application of Machine Learning models.

The application of machine learning models has been applied on input data [11]. The application of machine learning models has been furnished in figure 2.

Figure 2
Machine Learning models

6.2.1. Random Forest.

Input data set as available has to be applied to random forest algorithm. It has used 10 estimators that means 10 decision trees have been constructed and finally the average of these tree values has to be taken. The value of accuracy has been found as 88.89 % for criterion as gini index as well as for entropy.

6.2.2. Decision Tree.

Input data set as available has to be applied to decision tree algorithm. Criterion as gini index has been used. The value of accuracy has been found as 89 %.

6.2.3.KNN(K Nearest Neighbours) algorithm:

Input data set as available has to be applied to KNN(K Nearest Neighbours algorithm. Number of neighbours has been used as 5. Distance function is used as 'minkowski'. The value of accuracy has been found as 77.77%.

6.2.4. Support Vector Machine algorithm.

Input data set as available has to be applied to support vector machine algorithm. The value of accuracy has been found as 91.66 % based on kernel function as linear. The value of accuracy has been found as 94.44 % based on kernel function as radial basis.

6.2.5. Linear Regression.

Input data set as available has to be applied to logistic regression algorithm. The value of accuracy has been found as 100 %.

6.2.6. Logistic Regression.

Input data set [11] has to be applied to logistic regression algorithm. The value of accuracy has been found as 86.66 %.

6.2.7. Gaussian Naïve Bayes Algorithm.

Input data set [11] has to be applied to Gaussian Naïve Bayes algorithm. The value of accuracy has been found as 94.44 %.

6.2.8. Gradient Boosting Classifier Algorithm.

Input data set [11] has to be applied to Gradient Boosting Classifier algorithm. The value of accuracy has been found as 94.44 %.

6.3. Ensemble learning Techniques.

The application of ensemble learning techniques has been furnished in figure 3.

Simple Ensemble Techniques and Advanced Ensemble Techniques

Figure 3

6.3.1. Simple Ensemble Techniques.

Under simple ensemble based models, max voting, averaging and weighted averaging models have been used. Here decision tree classifier, K Nearest Neighbour Classifier and logistic regression models have been used. Under Max voting accuracy is 90.04 % on training data set and 69.23 % on tested data set, under averaging method, accuracy is 90.04 % on training data set and 25.00 % on tested data set and based on weighted average method, accuracy is 90.04 % on training data set and 26.92 % on tested data set.

6.3.2. Advanced Ensemble Techniques.

6.3.2.1. Blending.

Under blending, decision tree classifier, K Nearest Neighbour Classifier and logistic regression models have been used. Based on blending technique, accuracy is found to be 87.14 % on training data set and 66.35 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2. Bagging Meta Estimator.

6.3.2.2.1. Bagging Classifier.

Under bagging classifier, decision tree classifier has been used. The accuracy is found as 99.59 % on training data set and 74.04 % on tested data set.

Random Forest Classifier.

Under Random Forest Classifier, the accuracy is found as 100.00 % on training data set and 75.00 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2.2. Bagging Regressor.

Under bagging regressor, decision tree regressor has been used. The accuracy is found as 99.17 % on training data set and 68.27 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2. Boosting.

6.3.2.2.1. Adaboost(Adaptive Boosting) Classifier.

The accuracy is found as 82.99 % on training data set and 80.77 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2.2. Adaboost(Adaptive Boosting) Regressor.

The accuracy is found as 85.48 % on training data set and 68.27 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2.3. Gradient Boosting Classifier.

The accuracy is found as 75.93 % on training data set and 75.96 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2.4. Gradient Boosting Regressor.

The accuracy is found as 97.51 % on training data set and 75.96 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2.5. XGB(Extreme Gradient Boosting) Classifier.

The accuracy is found as 7.88 % on training data set and 16.34 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2.6. XGB(Extreme Gradient Boosting) Regressor.

The accuracy is found as 100.00 % on training data set and 66.35 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.2.7. Light GBM(Light Gradient Boosting Machine).

The accuracy is found as 57.26 % on training data set and 59.62 % on tested data set.

6.3.2.3. Stacking.

Under blending, decision tree classifier, K Nearest Neighbour Classifier as base model and logistic regression as final model has been used. Based on decision tree as base model, the accuracy is found as 99.59 % on training data set and 53.85 % on tested data set.

Based on K nearest neighbour as base model, the accuracy is found as 99.58 % on training data set and 62.5 % on tested data set.

Based on logistic regression as final model, the accuracy is found as 99.58 % on training data set and 63.46 % on tested data set.

6.4. Training and Test data.

The number of training data has been used as 70% and that of test data as 30% for the above models for better performance of the models.

7. Results.

The comparative study of all machine learning models on the basis of accuracy have been furnished in table 2 as furnished below. The classification report, confusion matrix of all the models have been furnished in table 3, table 4 respectively.

Table 2
Machine Learning models versus accuracy

No	Name of Machine Learning Model	Accuracy(%)
1.	Random Forest Algorithm	88.89 %
2.	Decision Tree Algorithm	89 %
3.	KNN(K-Nearest Neighbor) Algorithm	77.77 %
4.	Support Vector Machine with Linear Kernel	100 %
5.	Linear Regression Algorithm	100 %
6.	Gaussian Naïve Bayes Algorithm	94.44 %
7.	Logistic Regression	86.66 %
8.	Support Vector Machine with Radial Basis Kernel	94.44 %
9.	Gradient Boosting Classifier	94.44 %

Table 3

Classification Report Item wise based on Machine Learning Models

Model	Precision	Recall	f1-score	Support
Random Forest 0	0.91	0.91	0.91	11
Random Forest 1	0.86	0.86	0.86	7
Decision Tree 0	1.00	0.82	0.9	11
Decision Tree 1	0.78	1.00	0.88	7
KNN Classifier 0	0.82	0.82	0.82	11
KNN Classifier 1	0.71	0.71	0.71	7
SVM(Kernel=Linear) 0	1.00	1.00	1.00	11
SVM(Kernel=Linear) 1	1.00	1.00	1.00	7
Linear Regression 0	1.00	1.00	1.00	11
Linear Regression 1	1.00	1.00	1.00	7
Gaussian Naïve Bayes Algorithm 0	0.92	1.00	0.96	11
Gaussian Naïve Bayes Algorithm 1	1.00	0.86	0.92	7
Logistic Regression 0	0.90	0.90	0.90	11
Logistic Regression 1	0.80	0.80	0.80	7
SVM(Kernel=Radial Basis) 0	0.92	1.00	0.96	11
SVM(Kernel=Radial Basis) 1	1.00	0.86	0.92	7
Gradient Boosting Classifier 0	0.92	1.00	0.96	11
Gradient Boosting Classifier	11.00	0.86	0.92	7

Table 4
Confusion Matrix based on Machine Learning Models

Model Item	True Positive	False Positive	False Negative	True Negative
Random Forest 0	10	1	1	6
Random Forest 1	6	1	1	10
Decision Tree 0	9	2	0	7
Decision Tree 1	7	0	2	9
KNN Classifier 0	9	2	2	5
KNN Classifier 1	5	2	2	9
SVM(Kernel=Linear) 0	11	0	0	7

SVM(Kernel=Linear) 1	7	0	0	11
Linear Regression 0	10	1	1	6
Linear Regression 1	6	1	1	10
Gaussian Naïve Bayes 0	11	0	1	6
Gaussian Naïve Bayes 1	6	1	0	11
Logistic Regression 0	10	1	1	6
Logistic Regression 1	6	1	1	10
Gradient Boosting 0	11	0	1	6
Gradient Boosting 1	6	1	0	11

The preference of model has to be decided on the more value of accuracy. From table 2 it has been observed that the accuracy of support vector machine with linear kernel, linear regression is 100.00 % which is the maximum value among all models. Therefore, support vector machine with linear kernel, linear regression has to be preferred. Considering theoretical concept, support vector machine with linear kernel has to be considered as compared to linear regression.

The Change of values of accuracy has been furnished in graph named figure 4. The change of values of precision, recall, f1-score (classification report) and confusion matrix has been furnished in figure 5, figure 6 respectively.

Figure 4

Machine Learning model wise Accuracy

Figure 5
Machine Learning model wise Classification Report

Figure 6
Machine Learning model wise Confusion Matrix

The comparative study of simple ensemble techniques on the basis of accuracy has been furnished in table 5 as furnished below :-

Table 5
Simple Ensemble Techniques versus Accuracy

No	Name of Simple Ensemble Technique	Accuracy on Training data(%)	Accuracy on Tested data(%)
1	Max Voting	90.04	69.23
2	Averaging	90.04	25.00
3	Weighted Averaging	90.04	26.92

Advanced ensemble techniques include Stacking, Blending, Bagging and Boosting. Bagging includes Meta Estimator, Random Forest. Boosting includes Adaboost classifier, Adaboost Regressor, GBM classifier, GBM Regressor, XGBoost classifier, XGBoost Regressor, Light GBM.

The comparative study of advanced ensemble techniques on the basis of accuracy has been furnished in table 6 as furnished below :-

Table 6
Advanced Ensemble Techniques versus Accuracy

No	Name of Simple Ensemble Technique	Accuracy on Training data(%)	Accuracy on Tested data(%)
1	Blending	87.14	66.35
2	Bagging Classifier	99.59	74.04
3	Random Forest Classifier	<u>100.00</u>	<u>75.00</u>
4	Bagging Regressor	99.17	68.27
5	Adaboost Classifier	82.99	80.77
6	Adaboost Regressor	85.48	68.27
7	Gradient Boosting Classifier	75.93	75.96
8	Gradient Boosting Regressor	97.51	75.96
9	XGB Classifier	7.88	16.34
10	XGB Regressor	100.00	66.35
11	Light GBM	57.26	59.62
12	Stacking using KNN as base classifier	99.58	62.5
13	Stacking using DTree as base classifier	99.00	53.84
14	Stacking using Logistic Regression as final Classifier	99.58	63.46

The classification report, confusion matrix of simple ensemble techniques have been furnished in table 7, table 8 respectively.

Table 7
Classification Report Item wise based on Simple ensemble techniques

Model	Item	Precision	Recall	f1-score	Support
Max Voting	0	0.64	0.70	0.67	46
Max Voting	1	0.74	0.69	0.71	58
Averaging	0	0.36	0.57	0.44	46
Averaging	1	0	0	0	58
Weighted Averaging	0	0.36	0.61	0.45	46
Weighted Averaging	1	0	0	0	58

Table 8
Confusion Matrix based on Simple Ensemble Techniques

Model Item	True Positive	False Positive	False Negative	True Negative
Max Voting 0	32	14	18	40

Max Voting 1	40	18	14	32
Averaging 0	20	26	11	47
Averaging 1	47	11	26	20
Weighted Average 0	18	28	8	50
Weighted Average 1	50	8	28	18

The classification report, confusion matrix of simple ensemble techniques have been furnished in table 9, table 10 respectively.

The Change of values of accuracy based on simple ensemble techniques has been furnished in graph named figure 7. The change of values of precision, recall, f1-score (classification report) has been furnished in figure 8, the change of values in confusion matrix has been furnished in figure 9 respectively. The Change of values of accuracy based on advanced ensemble techniques has been furnished in graph named figure 10. The change of values of precision, recall, f1-score (classification report) of advanced ensemble techniques has been furnished in figure 11, the change of value in confusion matrix of these has been furnished in figure 12 respectively.

Table 9
Classification Report Item wise based on Advanced ensemble techniques

Model	Item	Precision	Recall	f1-score	Support
Blending	0	0.36	0.61	0.45	46
Blending	1	0	0	0	58
Bagging Classifier	0	0.73	0.65	0.69	46
Bagging Classifier	1	0.75	0.81	0.78	58
Random Forest Classifier	0	0.74	0.6	0.66	42
Random Forest Classifier	1	0.76	0.85	0.80	62
Bagging Regressor	0	0.62	0.57	0.59	42
Bagging Regressor	1	0.72	0.76	0.74	62
Adaboost Classifier	0	0.78	0.74	0.76	42
Adaboost Classifier	1	0.83	0.85	0.84	62
Adaboost Regressor	0	0.65	0.48	0.55	42
Adaboost Regressor	1	0.7	0.82	0.76	62
Gradient Boosting Classifier	0	0.79	0.55	0.65	42
Gradient Boosting Classifier	1	0.75	0.9	0.82	62
Gradient Boosting Regressor	0	0.71	0.69	0.7	42
Gradient Boosting Regressor	1	0.79	0.81	0.8	62
XGB Classifier	0	0.25	0.4	0.31	42
XGB Classifier	1	0	0	0	62
XGB Regressor	0	0.58	0.62	0.6	42
XGB Regressor	1	0.73	0.69	0.71	62
Light GBM	0	0	0	0	42
Light GBM	1	0.6	1.0	0.75	62
Stacking using KNN as base classifier	0	0	0	0	42

Stacking using KNN as base classifier	1	0.6	1.0	0.75	62
Stacking using DTree as base classifier	0	0	0	0	42
Stacking using DTree as base classifier	1	0.6	1.0	0.75	62
Stacking using Logistic Regression as final Classifier	0	0	0	0	42
Stacking using Logistic Regression as final Classifier	1	0.6	1.0	0.75	62

Table 10
Confusion Matrix based on Advanced Ensemble Techniques

Model Item	True Positive	False Positive	False Negative	True Negative
Blending 0	18	28	8	50
Blending 1	50	8	28	18
Bagging Classifier 0	30	16	11	47
Bagging Classifier 1	47	11	16	30
Random Forest Classifier 0	25	17	9	53
Random Forest Classifier 1	53	9	17	25
Bagging Regressor 0	24	18	15	47
Bagging Regressor 1	47	15	18	24
Adaboost Classifier 0	31	11	9	53
Adaboost Classifier 1	53	9	11	31
Adaboost Regressor 0	20	22	11	51
Adaboost Regressor 1	51	11	22	20
Gradient Boosting Classifier 0	29	13	12	50
Gradient Boosting Classifier 1	50	12	13	29
XGB Classifier 0	25	17	10	52
XGB Classifier 1	52	10	17	25
XGB Regressor 0	26	16	19	43
XGB Regressor 1	43	19	16	26
Light GBM 0	0	42	0	62

Light GBM 1	62	0	42	0
Stacking using KNN as base classifier 0	0	42	0	62
Stacking using KNN as base classifier 1	62	0	42	0
Stacking using DTree as base classifier 0	0	42	0	62
Stacking using DTree as base classifier 1	62	0	42	0
Stacking using Logistic Regression as final Classifier 0	0	42	0	62
Stacking using Logistic Regression as final Classifier 1	62	0	42	0

The comparative study of final advanced ensemble techniques on the basis of accuracy has been furnished in table 11 as furnished below. The Change of values of accuracy based on final ensemble ensemble techniques has been furnished in graph named figure 13.

Table 11

Comparison of Random Forest Classifier with Max voting in terms of accuracy on Training data set and Tested data set

No	Name of Ensemble Technique	Accuracy on Training data(%)	Accuracy on Tested data(%)
1	Max Voting	90.04	69.23
2	Random Forest Classifier	<u>100.00</u>	<u>75.00</u>

Figure 7

Simple Ensemble Technique wise Accuracy on Training Data and Tested Data

Figure 8

Simple ensemble technique wise Precision, Recall, F1 Score, Support

Figure 9

Simple Ensemble Technique wise True Positive, False Positive and True Negative

Figure 10

Advanced Ensemble Techniques versus Accuracy on Training and Tested Data

Figure 11

Advanced Ensemble Technique wise Precision, Recall, F1 Score and Support

Figure 12

Advanced Ensemble Technique based True Positive, False Positive, False Negative, True Negative

Figure 13

Performance of Random Forest Classifier with Max Voting in terms of Training data set and Tested Data set

8. Conclusion.

From table 2, it has been observed that performance of Support vector machine with linear kernel and linear regression model is excellent as compared to other models. The advantage of Support vector machine with linear kernel is that it can perform well at classifying non-linear data, it can reduce the overfitting of data, it can learn without a local minima, it can perform well on data sets that have many attributes.

The advantage of linear regression is simple Implementation, performs best on Linear Data, overfitting can be reduced by regularization. Comparing these the preference of Support vector machine with linear kernel is more than linear regression.

From table 5, it has been observed that the performance of max voting is better as compared to other models. From table 6, it has been observed that the performance of random forest classifier is better as compared to other models. The accuracy of random forest classifier on training data set is 100 % in training data and 75 % in tested data. However, the accuracy of XGB regressor is 100 % on training data set and 66.35 % on tested data set. Considering the performance of training data set and tested data set, random forest classifier is preferable than XGB regressor. The performance of Max voting classifier is 90.04 % on training data and 69.23 % on tested data. Comparing with of random forest classifier, it has been found that random forest classifier is the best ensemble technique among others. The advantage of random forest classifier is that it is

Robust to Overfitting, it can handle missing Values, it can give feature Importance i.e. It can provide insights into those features which are most influential in predictions, it can help in aiding feature selection. Random Forest can handle large datasets with numerous features and data points, making it versatile for various applications.

Considering all these points, it is preferable to choose random forest classifier for prediction of lever disease.

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